

Effects of Salinity Stress on Germination and Seedling Growth in Sesame Genotypes

Rüstem ÜSTÜN^{1*}

¹ Akdeniz University, Faculty of Agriculture, Department of Field Crops, Antalya

*Corresponding author: rustemustun@akdeniz.edu.tr

Abstract

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is one of the most significant oilseed crops, known for its highly valued edible oil. Salinity is one of the critical factors affecting plant growth among various abiotic stresses, particularly during germination and early developmental stages. The increasing use of saline water for irrigation has exacerbated this challenge, necessitating the identification of salt-tolerant genotypes. This study investigated the effects of different salinity levels on germination and early seedling development in sesame by applying four NaCl concentrations (50 mM, 100 mM, 150 mM, and 200 mM) along with a control group. The salt tolerance of various sesame genotypes was assessed based on key developmental parameters, including germination percentage, mean germination time, relative injury rate, seedling height, water uptake percentage, seedling fresh weight, biomass, and overall salt tolerance level. The results indicated that seedling height was the most sensitive indicator of salinity stress, whereas biomass was the least affected parameter. Notably, increasing salinity levels significantly impacted early growth, while lower salinity levels (50 mM) did not exhibit a substantial adverse effect, suggesting mild tolerance in certain sesame varieties. This study provides valuable insights for selecting salt-tolerant sesame genotypes, facilitating improved cultivation strategies in saline-prone agricultural regions. This analysis showed a significant change in early development stages with an increase in salinity levels, but lower salinity levels (50mM) did not exhibit adverse effects, suggesting mild salinity tolerance against saline environments in different sesame varieties. This study suggested reliable information for selecting the suitable sesame genotype to grow according to the saline conditions of farmers' soils.

Research Article

Article History

Received	:27.02.2025
Accepted	:30.03.2025

Keywords

Sesame
salinity stress
germination
seedling

1. Introduction

Sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) is a significant oilseed crop renowned for its high-quality edible oil and essential fatty acid content, making it a valuable component of both human nutrition and industrial applications (Pathak et al., 2021). The seeds are notably rich in oil, comprising approximately 45–55%, and contain about 20–25% protein, positioning sesame as a nutritionally dense food source (Wan et al., 2023). Sesame oil is characterized by a high proportion of unsaturated fatty acids, particularly oleic and linoleic acids, and contains unique lignan compounds such as sesamin and sesamol, which are known to enhance oxidative stability and confer health benefits (Zheng et al., 2021). Sesame seeds are used extensively in producing cooking oil and tahini and find applications in the cosmetic, pharmaceutical, and chemical industries due to their bioactive compounds and functional properties (Dossa et al., 2017). Despite its considerable nutritional and economic value, sesame remains underexploited, primarily due to agronomic constraints such as low yield potential, susceptibility to various biotic and abiotic stresses, seed shattering, and an indeterminate growth habit (Cui et al., 2021). Abiotic and biotic stress factors negatively affect seed germination, plant growth, yield and various quality traits in plants. Abiotic stress encompasses extreme temperature fluctuations, drought, flooding, salinity, heavy metal toxicity, and nutrient imbalances, each eliciting distinct physiological and biochemical responses (Zhang et al., 2020). Among these, extreme temperatures, drought, and saline soils are the primary environmental constraints affecting plant survival and distribution in natural ecosystems (Zhang et al., 2022). Salinity stress, resulting from high concentrations of soluble salts in the soil, poses a significant challenge by disrupting plant growth and development, ultimately reducing agricultural productivity (Munns and Tester, 2008). Plants exhibit considerable variation in their tolerance to salinity, with some species being highly susceptible to salt stress while others demonstrate relative resilience. This

variation arises from multiple factors. Certain plant species have evolved adaptive mechanisms to regulate osmotic pressure in response to saline conditions. Salinity stress adversely impacts sesame by disrupting osmotic balance, ion homeostasis, and metabolic activity during early growth stages (Khatun et al., 2019). Germination and seedling growth are particularly sensitive to salt stress, as these stages are critical for stand establishment and subsequent crop yield (Jamil et al., 2022). The inhibition of water uptake due to osmotic stress and toxic effects of excessive sodium (Na^+) and chloride (Cl^-) ions reduce germination rate, seedling vigor, and root-shoot development (Ashraf et al., 2021). Moreover, genotypic variation plays a pivotal role in determining the extent of salinity tolerance, with some sesame genotypes exhibiting better adaptability through ion exclusion, osmotic adjustment, or antioxidant responses (Yasmeen et al., 2023). Sesame, a widely cultivated crop in arid and semi-arid regions, is particularly sensitive to soil salinity, with its susceptibility increasing when the salt contains calcium chloride (Nassery et al., 1979; Cerda et al., 1997). Understanding the germination process of sesame is crucial, as it represents the initial and most critical stage in the plant's life cycle (Yadav et al., 2022). Germination directly affects stand establishment and, consequently, overall yield. Previous studies have reported varying responses of sesame seeds to different salinity and temperature levels, highlighting the need for a comprehensive investigation. Bahrami and Razmjoo (2012a) found that increasing water electrical conductivity (EC) significantly inhibited germination and early seedling growth in sesame cultivars. Similarly, El Harfi et al. (2016) observed that while salinity and drought stress negatively impacted sesame germination and seedling growth, drought stress exerted a more pronounced inhibitory effect. Both stress factors had a more significant impact on seedling growth than germination. Understanding the effect of salinity stress on sesame seed germination is crucial for improving crop productivity in saline-prone environments. Despite these

findings, research on the salinity of sesame seed germination remains limited, underscoring the need for further investigation. Understanding the physiological responses of different sesame genotypes under salinity stress at early growth stages is crucial for identifying tolerant lines and guiding breeding programs aimed at enhancing salt tolerance. Recent advances in phenotyping and stress physiology have facilitated the screening of sesame genotypes based on germination indices, seedling biomass, and ion accumulation profiles under salt stress (Zhang et al., 2020). This study aims to investigate the impact of salinity stress on the germination characteristics of sesame seeds. Specifically, the research examines how varying salinity levels in the germination medium influence germination rate, seedling vigor, and other key germination parameters. Insights from this study will contribute to a deeper understanding of sesame's salinity tolerance and help develop strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of salinity on sesame cultivation.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant materials and sterilization of seeds

The sesame genotypes were obtained from different regions of the world; KU-21 (Japan), TS5 (Pakistan), PI 238420 (USDA), PI 170728 (USDA), and PI 207064 (USDA). The study was conducted at the Department of Field Crops, Faculty of Agriculture, Akdeniz University, Antalya, Türkiye. Essential materials, including Whatman paper, sodium hydrochloride, sodium hypochlorite, and petri dishes, were obtained from the molecular laboratory of the same department. The seed sterilization procedure was carried out by Hassen et al. (2009), which sterilized the seeds before placing them in petri dishes. 150 seeds with uniform size, shape and color were taken from each genotype and disinfected with sodium hypochlorite. At first, seeds were completed with %2 NaOCl twice to get complete disinfestation. Successively, flowing deionized water was used for two minutes to eliminate the chemicals from the seed surface.

2.2. Salt solution preparation and design of the experiment

Four separate flasks were cleaned to prepare the NaCl solutions. Each flask was filled with the predetermined volume of distilled water, as calculated in the experimental design. The required amounts of NaCl were precisely measured using an analytical weighing balance to obtain solutions with the desired concentrations of 50 mM, 100 mM, 150 mM, and 200 mM. The calculated NaCl mass was carefully added to the distilled water flasks. Each solution was mixed for 15 minutes using an electronic stirrer for dissolution and uniform distribution. Additionally, a separate flask containing only distilled water was prepared as the control treatment for comparison. A completely randomized design (CRD) was employed in this experiment, consisting of five distinct treatments and a control group, each with three replicates. Petri dishes with a diameter of 9 cm were sterilized using an autoclave to minimize the risk of fungal contamination. Two layers of Whatman filter paper were placed within each sterilized dish to serve as a germination medium. Subsequently, 5 ml of the prepared solution was carefully added to each dish's filter paper. The experiment involved five treatments: T0 (control, containing only distilled water with 0mM NaCl concentration), T1 (50mM NaCl), T2 (100mM NaCl), T3 (150mM NaCl), and T4 (200mM NaCl). Each treatment group consisted of three replications. Ten seeds with uniform size and characteristics were placed at equal distances within each dish to ensure consistent testing conditions. The Petri dishes were placed in a controlled environment with a temperature range between 20 °C and 22.1 °C. Each Petri dish was wrapped with parafilm and stored in a dark environment to minimize water loss due to evaporation and maintain consistent moisture levels.

2.3. Assessment of germination and seedling growth

Daily monitoring of seed germination was conducted throughout the 7-day experimental period. Germination was identified by the emergence of a primary root exceeding 2 mm

in length beyond the seed coat (pericarp). Following the experiment's conclusion, the sesame seedlings were carefully preserved to facilitate careful data collection. This data collection process involved measuring several key parameters, including fresh weight, dry weight, and seedling length. By analyzing these parameters, we assessed the impact of the various treatments on seedling growth and development. This comprehensive evaluation provided valuable insights into the seedlings' physiological, phenotypic, and biomass characteristics under the specific experimental conditions employed in this study.

2.3.1. Water uptake percentage

Water uptake by the seedlings was indirectly estimated by analyzing the difference between their fresh weight and dry weight.

Water Uptake %age = [(Fresh weight – dry weight)/Fresh weight] × 100.

2.3.2. Mean germination time

The number of germinated seeds from each replication was counted daily, and the mean value was determined. The overall mean germination time was calculated using the following formula:

Mean Germination Time = $\sum Dn / \sum n$

In this formula, 'n' represents the count of seeds that germinated on a specific day 'D,' where 'D' indicates the number of days since the germination process began.

2.3.3. Germination percentage

Germination data was collected daily for 10 days, and the germination time was determined at the end of this period. The germination percentage was calculated using the following formula:

Germination Percentage = $\frac{\text{Number of Germinated Seeds}}{\text{Total Number of Sown Seeds}} \times 100$

2.3.4. Relative injury rate

The relative injury rate was calculated using the formula established by Tsegay and Gebreslassie in 2014. This involved subtracting the germination percentage of salt-treated seeds from the germination percentage

of the control seeds, and then dividing the result by the germination percentage of the control seeds.

Rate of Relative Injury = $\frac{[\% \text{age of germination in control} - \% \text{age of germination in salt treatments}]}{\% \text{age of germination in control}}$.

2.3.5. Seedling length reduction

Seedling length reduction in germinated seedlings is measured as the percentage decrease in both root and shoot lengths, which signifies a delay in growth and slower early growth. This reduction is determined using the following equation.

Reduction in seedling length = $\frac{[(\text{Seedling length in control} - \text{Seedling length in salt-treated}) / \text{Seedling length in control}] \times 100}{}$.

2.3.6. Seedling biomass

To ensure consistent and reliable measurements, seedling biomass was determined using an analytical balance. Prior to weighing, the seedlings underwent a drying process in an oven at 55 °C for 48 hours.

2.3.7. Salinity tolerance level

The determination of the salt tolerance level was determined with the help of the prescribed standard formula provided hereafter.

Level of Salt Tolerance = $\frac{(\text{dry weight of treated seedlings} / \text{dry weight of control seedlings}) \times 100}{}$.

3. Results

Salinity stress significantly influenced the germination rate and all seedling growth traits in this study (Table 1). There are also significant interactions among sesame cultivars under salinity stress conditions. Salinity is a major abiotic stress factor in plant science, significantly affecting seed germination, plant development, and overall crop productivity, thereby posing a substantial constraint on agricultural yields. This study examined the effects of varying NaCl concentrations on germination and early seedling growth across different sesame genotypes. The findings indicated no statistically significant difference in germination percentage between the control

group (0 mM NaCl) and seeds exposed to 50 mM NaCl. However, as salinity levels increased, germination rates declined markedly across all genotypes. Among the treatments, T4 exhibited the most pronounced reduction in germination. Specifically, in the T4 treatment, the PI 207064 and KU-21 genotypes demonstrated the lowest germination rates, reducing approximately 64% (Table 1). Across treatments, most recorded parameters exhibit highly significant variation in genotype analysis (Table 1), aligning with the overall treatment-wise assessment (Table 3). However, significant genotype-specific differences are observed only for fresh weight, water uptake percentage, and salt tolerance levels (Table 2). In contrast, other attributes including biomass, germination percentage, mean germination time, seedling height, height reduction, and relative injury rates remain statistically indistinguishable among genotypes (Table 2). The progressive impact of treatment intensifies from the control condition to the 50 mM dose, with a pronounced significance increase at higher concentrations (Table 3). Germination percentage remained consistently high across all genotypes under lower to moderate salinity conditions, from the control to 50 mM, 100 mM, and 150 mM. However, a substantial decline was observed at the highest salinity level of 200 mM (Table 3). The most pronounced reduction occurred in KU-21 and PI 207064, where germination dropped from 100% under control conditions and T1 to 36.67% at T4 (Table 1). Similarly, TS5 declined from 100% to 73.33% at T4, while PI 238420 decreased from 96.67% at T0 to 63.33% at T4. Genotypes 3 and 4 experienced a decline to 63.44% at T4 from initial values of 96.67% and 100%, respectively (Table 1). A cumulative analysis further confirmed this trend, with germination rates decreasing from 98.67% at 0 and 50 mM to 40% at 200 mM (Table 3). Additionally, genotype-wise cumulative analysis revealed significant differences among genotypes, with PI 170728 exhibiting the highest germination rate at 92%, whereas KU-21 recorded the lowest at 76% (Table 2). Seedling height progressively

declined with increasing salinity levels across all genotypes. The seedling height in KU-21 ranges from 2.133 cm at T0 to 1.000 cm at T4. Similar trends were observed across other genotypes, indicating that elevated salinity levels significantly inhibit seedling growth. The height reduction rate intensified, with PI 207064 experiencing the most pronounced decline at T4 (Table 1). A comprehensive treatment-wise analysis further confirmed this trend, demonstrating a decrease in seedling height from 2.56 cm at 0 mM to 1.16 cm at 200 mM (Table 3). Additionally, the cumulative analysis revealed genotype-specific variations, with PI 207064 exhibiting the most significant cumulative seedling height at 2.11 cm, whereas KU-21 recorded the lowest at 1.57 cm (Table 2). Mean germination time increased with rising salinity levels, indicating delayed germination under stress conditions. For instance, in KU-21, the mean germination time extended from 34 hours at T0 to 108 hours at T4. Similar trends were observed across other genotypes, highlighting the inhibitory effect of higher salinity levels on the germination process. TS5, for example, exhibited an increase in mean germination time from 36 hours at T0 to 108 hours at T4, further reinforcing the overall trend of delayed germination in saline environments (Table 1). Among treatments, the shortest germination time was recorded at 0 mM (36 hours), whereas the longest was observed at 200 mM (108 hours) (Table 3). Genotype-wise cumulative analysis revealed that KU-21, PI 238420, and PI 207064 had the shortest germination times (64 hours), whereas TS5 and PI 170728 exhibited the longest at 68 hours (Table 2). The relative injury rate further reflected the detrimental effects of salinity stress. KU-21 and TS5 exhibited a relative injury rate of zero at lower salinity levels, indicating their initial resilience to mild saline conditions. However, as salinity increased to T4, relative injury rates rose sharply. In KU-21, the injury rate escalated from 0.000 at T0 to 1.000 at T4, signifying heightened stress and damage induced by salinity. Similarly, TS5 demonstrated a notable increase in relative injury rate at T4, underscoring the adverse

impact of elevated salinity levels (Table 1). A comprehensive treatment-wise analysis revealed a rise in relative injury rate from 0 at 0 mM to 60 at 200 mM (Table 3). Meanwhile,

genotype-wise analysis showed no statistically significant differences, with the highest value recorded in Genotype-1 (23.33) and the lowest in Genotype-4 (8) (Table 2).

Table 1. Analysis of variance of varieties in accordance with applied salinity levels. Germination percentage (G.P.), seedling height (S.H.), height reduction (H.R.), relative injury rate (R.I.R.), mean germination time (M.G.T.), fresh weight (F.W.), water uptake percentage (W.U.P.), and salt tolerance level (S.T.L.).

Genot ype	Treat ment	G.P.	S.H. (cm)	H.R. (cm)	R.I.R.	M.G.T. (hours)	F.W. (g)	Biomass (g)	W.U.P.	S.T.L.
KU- 21	T0	96.667±3. 333a	2.133±0. 088a	100.000± 0.000a	0.000±0. 000b	34.000±0. 000c	0.304±0. 001a	0.105±0. 001a	82.700±0. 284a	100.000±0. .000a
	T1	100.000± 0.000a	1.900±0. 058b	79.883±5. 201b	0.000±0. 000b	40.000±4. 000c	0.284±0. 001b	0.104±0. 001a	81.640±0. 083ab	99.212±0. 004ab
	T2	100.000± 0.000a	1.533±0. 058c	47.970±6. 344c	0.000±0. 000b	56.000±8. 000bc	0.264±0. 001c	0.103±0. 001ab	80.523±0. 179bc	97.632±0. 012abc
	T3	96.667±3. 333a	1.303±0. 009c	27.193±2. 708d	0.167±0. 033ab	80.000±8. 000b	0.251±0. 006d	0.100±0. 001bc	80.030±0. 497cd	95.110±0. 013bc
	T4	36.667±1 7.628b	1.000±0. 000d	0.000±0.0 00e	1.000±0. 033a	108.000± 4.000a	0.234±0. 001e	0.098±0. 000c	78.958±0. 027d	93.520±0. 011c
TSS	T0	100.000± 0.000a	2.600±0. 058a	100.000± 0.000a	0.000±0. 000b	36.000±0. 000d	0.367±0. 001a	0.111±0. 001a	84.817±0. 056a	100.000±0. .000a
	T1	100.000± 0.000a	2.167±0. 033b	72.973±1. 286b	0.000±0. 000b	44.000±4. 000cd	0.329±0. 002b	0.110±0. 001ab	83.357±0. 154b	98.355±0. 004ab
	T2	83.333±0. 033ab	1.767±0. 033c	48.170±3. 625c	0.033±0. 033b	64.000±8. 000bc	0.274±0. 001c	0.108±0. 000ab	80.190±0. 072c	97.461±0. 005ab
	T3	76.667±0. 033b	1.307±0. 018d	19.167±0. 833d	0.200±0. 058b	88.000±8. 000ab	0.257±0. 001d	0.105±0. 002b	79.530±0. 384c	94.323±0. 018bc
	T4	73.333±0. 033b	1.200±0. 000d	12.530±0. 454d	0.633±0. 445a	108.000± 4.000a	0.242±0. 000e	0.096±0. 001c	80.063±0. 237c	86.672±0. 005
PI 23842 0	T0	96.667±3. 333a	2.400±0. 057a	100.000± 0.000a	0.000±0. 000b	36.000±0. 000c	0.187±0. 001a	0.056±0. 004a	85.000±0. 946a	100.000±0. .000a
	T1	96.667±3. 333a	2.133±0. 033b	81.220±3. 958b	0.033±0. 033b	40.000±4. 000c	0.164±0. 001b	0.048±0. 001ab	85.440±0. 422a	85.843±0. 062ab
	T2	96.667±3. 333a	1.600±0. 057c	42.663±2. 372c	0.033±0. 033b	56.000±8. 000bc	0.144±0. 001c	0.044±0. 001bc	84.847±0. 299a	78.132±0. 039b
	T3	90.000±0. 000a	1.263±0. 018d	18.963±2. 063d	0.100±0. 000ab	80.000±8. 000b	0.128±0. 001d	0.043±0. 001bc	83.073±0. 274ab	77.547±0. 038b
	T4	63.333±3. 333b	1.200±0. 000d	14.333±0. 592d	0.367±0. 033a	108.000± 4.000a	0.103±0. 001e	0.039±0. 001c	81.293±0. 342b	69.533±0. 041a
PI 17072 8	T0	100.000± 0.000a	2.667±0. 088a	100.000± 0.000a	0.000±0. 000b	36.000±0. 000d	0.209±0. 001a	0.054±0. 000a	87.130±0. 070a	100.000±0. .000a
	T1	96.667±3. 333a	2.233±0. 033b	74.380±3. 987b	0.033±0. 033b	44.000±4. 000cd	0.155±0. 000b	0.052±0. 001ab	83.063±0. 192b	97.834±0. 013ab
	T2	100.000± 0.000a	2.000±0. 000c	60.350±3. 297c	0.000±0. 000b	64.000±8. 000bc	0.146±0. 003c	0.051±0. 001bc	82.570±0. 503b	94.413±0. 014bc
	T3	100.000± 0.000a	1.533±0. 033cd	32.023±1. 307d	0.000±0. 000b	88.000±8. 000ab	0.141±0. 001cd	0.049±0. 000c	82.586±0. 134c	91.615±0. 000c
	T4	63.333±1 2.019b	1.200±0. 000e	12.067±0. 659e	0.367±0. 120a	108.000± 4.000a	0.138±0. 001d	0.045±0. 000d	83.637±0. 104c	83.850±0. 003d
PI 20706 4	T0	100.000± 0.000a	3.000±0. 058a	100.000± 0.000a	0.000±0. 000b	36.000±0. 000c	0.178±0. 002a	0.052±0. 001a	85.490±0. 208a	100.000±0. .000a
	T1	100.000± 0.000a	2.733±0. 033b	86.727±1. 387b	0.000±0. 000b	40.000±4. 000c	0.151±0. 001b	0.048±0. 000b	83.883±0. 138ab	94.202±0. 014ab
	T2	93.333±3. 333a	2.033±0. 033c	51.670±0. 838c	0.067±0. 058b	56.000±8. 000bc	0.138±0. 002c	0.045±0. 001c	83.693±0. 337b	87.084±0. 022bc
	T3	90.000±5. 774a	1.600±0. 058cd	29.970±2. 536d	0.100±0. 058b	80.000±8. 000b	0.135±0. 002c	0.042±0. 000c	84.323±0. 067b	82.219±0. 013c
	T4	36.667±8. 819b	1.200±0. 000d	10.017±0. 292e	0.633±0. 088a	108.000± 4.000a	0.089±0. 001d	0.038±0. 001d	78.930±0. 494c	72.858±0. 022d

Values having common letter(s) within a column of similar treatments do not differ significantly according to LSD test at p<0.05.” and with different letters (superscripts) showing significant difference.

Fresh weight progressively declined with increasing salinity levels, indicating a reduction in seedling growth and development.

In KU-21, fresh weight decreased from 0.304 g at T0 to 0.234 g at T4, a trend similar to that observed across other genotypes. For instance,

TS5 declined from 0.367 g at T0 to 0.242 g at T4 (Table 1). A treatment-wise analysis revealed an overall reduction in fresh weight across all varieties, dropping from 0.248 g under control conditions to 0.161 g at T4 (Table 3). Genotype-wise analysis indicated significant variation among varieties, with TS5 recording the highest cumulative fresh weight (0.294 g), while PI 207064 exhibited the lowest (0.138 g) (Table 2). Biomass exhibited a declining trend, with KU-21's biomass decreasing from 0.105 g at T0 to 0.098 g at T4. The concurrent reduction in fresh weight and biomass across genotypes underscores salinity's detrimental impact on sesame seedlings' overall growth (Table 1). However,

a treatment-wise analysis revealed that the overall variation was statistically non-significant, with only a slight decline from 0.076 g under control conditions to 0.063 g at T4 (Table 3). Genotype-wise analysis indicated substantial variation, with TS5 recording the highest cumulative biomass (0.106 g), while PI 207064 exhibited the lowest (0.044 g) (Table 2). Water uptake percentage declined progressively with increasing salinity levels. PI 207064 exhibited the most pronounced reduction, decreasing from 85.49% at T0 to 78.93% at T4. Similarly, KU-21 experienced a decline from 82.70% at T0 to 78.96% at T4 (Table 1).

Table 2. Pair-wise multiple comparison of means of all the 5 genotypes for studied traits. Germination percentage (G.P.), seedling height (S.H.), height reduction (H.R.), relative injury rate (R.I.R.), mean germination time (M.G.T.), fresh weight (F.W.), water uptake percentage (W.U.P.), and salt tolerance level (S.T.L.)

Parameters	KU-21	TS5	PI 238420	PI 170728	PI 207064	Significance
G.P.	76.000±10.319a	82.667±7.202a	88.667±3.634a	92.000±4.386a	84.000±6.676a	0.5336
S. H. (cm)	1.574±0.110a	1.808±0.141a	1.719±0.128a	1.927±0.139a	2.113±0.181a	0.0911
H. R. (cm)	51.009±9.682a	50.568±8.796a	51.436±9.107a	55.764±8.328a	55.677±9.031a	0.9872
R.I.R.	23.333±0.104a	17.333±0.072a	10.667±0.037a	8.000±0.044a	16.000±0.067a	0.5579
M.G.T (hours)	64.000±7.468a	68.000±7.468a	64.000±7.468a	68.000±7.468a	64.000±7.468a	0.9856
F.W. (g)	0.268±0.007a	0.294±0.012a	0.145±0.008b	0.158±0.007b	0.138±0.008b	<.0001*
Biomass (g)	0.102±0.001a	0.106±0.001a	0.046±0.002b	0.050±0.001bc	0.044±0.001c	<.0001*
W.U.P.	80.770±0.361a	81.591±0.567a	83.931±0.458ab	83.797±0.467bc	83.264±0.613c	<.0001*
S.T.L.	97.091±0.744a	95.364±1.308ab	82.211±3.159ab	93.543±1.542bc	87.272±2.593c	<.0001*

Values having common letter(s) within a column of similar treatments do not differ significantly according to LSD test at $p < 0.05$ and with different letters (superscripts) showing significant difference.

A treatment-wise analysis revealed an overall reduction in water uptake, decreasing from 85.03% at 0 mM to 80.58% at 200 mM (Table 3). Genotype-wise cumulative analysis showed that PI 238420 had the highest water uptake percentage (83.93%), while KU-21 recorded the lowest (80.77%) (Table 2). Salt tolerance varied among genotypes, with KU-21 and TS5 demonstrating relatively higher tolerance at moderate salinity levels. For instance, KU-21 maintained a salt tolerance of 95.11% at T3, while TS5 exhibited a tolerance

of 94.32% at the same salinity level. In contrast, PI 207064 displayed the lowest tolerance, experiencing a significant decline at T4, with salt tolerance dropping to 72.86% (Table 1). A treatment-wise analysis revealed an overall reduction in salt tolerance, decreasing from 100.00% at 0 mM to 81.29% at 200 mM (Table 3). Similarly, the genotype-wise analysis showed a notable decline, with KU-21 maintaining the highest tolerance (97.09%) and PI 207064 exhibiting the lowest (87.27%) (Table 2).

Table 3. Pair-wise multiple comparison of means of all the 5 treatments for studied traits. Germination percentage (G.P.), seedling height (S.H.), height reduction (H.R.), relative injury rate (R.I.R.), mean germination time (M.G.T.), fresh weight (F.W.), water uptake percentage (W.U.P.), and salt tolerance level (S.T.L.).

Treatment	G.P.	S.H. (cm)	H.R. (cm)	R.I.R.	M.G.T. (hours)	F.W. (g)	Biomass (g)	W.U.P.	S.T.L.
0mM	98.667±0 .908a	2.560±0. 081a	100.000± 0.000a	0.000±0. 000a	36.000±0. 000a	0.248±0. 020a	0.076±0. 007a	85.027± 0.417a	100.000± 0.000a
50mM	98.667±0 .908a	2.233±0. 075b	79.037±1. 880b	1.333±0. 009b	41.600±1. 600ab	0.217±0. 020ab	0.073±0. 008a	83.477± 0.340b	95.090±1. 720ab
100mM	87.333±1 .182a	1.787±0. 056c	50.165±2. 112c	2.667±0. 012b	59.200±3. 200c	0.193±0. 017ab	0.070±0. 008a	82.365± 0.494bc	90.943±2. 158bc
150mM	88.667±2 .264a	1.401±0. 039d	25.463±1. 648d	11.333±0 .024b	83.200±3. 200cd	0.182±0. 016ab	0.068±0. 008a	81.909± 0.505c	88.163±2. 029cd
200mM	40.000±7 .368b	1.160±0. 021e	9.789±1.3 70e	60.000±0 .074b	108.000± 0.000d	0.161±0. 017b	0.063±0. 008a	80.576± 0.483d	81.287±2. 509d
Significance	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*	<.0001*	0.0116*	0.8189	<.0001*	<.0001*

Values having common letter(s) within a column of similar treatments do not differ significantly according to LSD test at $p < 0.05$ and with different letters (superscripts) showing significant difference.

4. Discussion

Several studies have shown that moderate salinity levels have minimal impact on seed germination and plant growth in sesame (Bahrami et al., 2012b; Abbasdokht et al., 2012) and soybean (Açıkbaş et al., 2023). However, these studies also demonstrate that higher salinity levels negatively impact these parameters (Shanko et al., 2017; Açıkbaş et al., 2023). Our findings are consistent with this established trend, suggesting a moderate level of salt tolerance in sesame during germination (Munns and Tester, 2008; Bahrami and Razmjoo, 2012a). While our study aligns with previous research on moderate salinity, it is well-documented that high salinity levels can significantly inhibit seed germination. This is likely due to the detrimental effects of sodium (Na^+) and chloride (Cl^-) ions, which can disrupt the water balance and metabolic processes within the seeds (Huang and Redmann, 1995; Flowers and Flowers, 2005; Ramirez et al., 2005). These findings highlight the varied responses of sesame genotypes to salinity stress during germination. This knowledge provides valuable insights for further research on developing stress-tolerant sesame varieties and improving crop improvement strategies in saline environments. Several studies have demonstrated that seed health and size play a critical role in water uptake during germination and early seedling development (Tabatabaei

and Naghibalghora, 2014; Hussain and Kumar, 2022). The decrease in water uptake percentage observed with increasing salinity is thought to be due to two main factors: dehydration of the cell cytoplasm due to high sodium chloride concentrations in the soil and decreased seed coat permeability (Bahrami et al., 2012b). As salinity levels rise, the seed coat may become less permeable to water, further hindering water absorption. The higher salinity levels restrict water uptake during the crucial cell division and differentiation stages by increasing osmotic pressure within the plant cells (Voigt et al., 2009). This elevated osmotic pressure in the soil solution creates a barrier to water uptake by seedlings, ultimately reducing their overall water absorption capacity (Hussain and Kumar, 2022). A well-documented phenomenon in crops grown under saline conditions is a reduction in seedling height. This is attributed to high salt concentrations' dehydrating and shrinking effects on plant cells (Flowers, 2004). This study explored the impact of varying NaCl concentrations on seedling height reduction across different sesame genotypes. A significant increase in height reduction with higher salinity levels was observed in this study. Interestingly, the degree of height reduction varied amongst the genotypes studied (Nobre et al., 2010), highlighting potential variations in salt tolerance among sesame varieties. Previous studies on sesame

have demonstrated the detrimental effects of salinity stress on various growth parameters. It has been found that seed germination (Cuartero and Fernandez, 1999), plant height (Bekele et al., 2017), shoot dry weight (Essa, 2002), and seedling fresh weight (Farhoudi and Tafti, 2011) are negatively affected by saline environments. Studies have also shown a decrease in germination percentage when exposed to salinity stress (Ahmadvand et al., 2012; Ndifon, 2013). Moreover, recent studies confirm that both plant height and root length are negatively affected by salinity (Ahmed et al., 2023). The stress effect increased with increasing salt concentration, and higher levels led to a significant decrease in shoot dry weight (Le et al., 2021). These findings also highlight the complex relationship between salinity and seed traits in sesame. By revealing how seed quality can affect water uptake capacity, it provides valuable insights for future research on stress tolerance and crop improvement strategies in saline environments. Our findings illuminate the diverse reactions of sesame genotypes to salinity stress, providing critical data to unravel the mechanisms behind salt-induced growth inhibition (Santos et al., 2012). The observed differences in seedling height among genotypes under saline conditions warrant further exploration and offer valuable insights for formulating strategies to improve sesame stress tolerance during cultivation. These results corroborate the notion that sesame exhibits moderate salt tolerance. However, high salinity levels can still significantly reduce seedling height. This decrease is likely a consequence of diminished cell division and elongation processes under salt stress (Voigt et al., 2009). Reduced seedling height can have cascading adverse effects on plant growth. It can lead to delayed leaf emergence and reduced leaf size, ultimately hindering photosynthesis and overall plant productivity (El Harfi et al., 2016). Our understanding of the precise mechanisms by which salt affects seed germination remains incomplete. However, it is well-established that high salinity disrupts plant growth through various pathways. Increased salinity levels create an osmotic

imbalance, hindering a plant's capacity to absorb water essential for growth (Bekele et al., 2017). This osmotic stress restricts water uptake and cell expansion, limiting plant development (Tafouo et al., 2010). Furthermore, high salinity disrupts the delicate balance of ions like potassium (K^+), sodium (Na^+), their ratio (K^+/Na^+), calcium (Ca^{2+}), and chloride (Cl^-) within plant cells, leading to a cascade of physiological changes (Flowers and Flowers, 2005). The accumulation of sodium and chloride ions in plant tissues disrupts essential physiological processes and hinders the uptake of vital nutrients (Shitole and Dhumal, 2012). Research suggests that both osmotic stress (Kingsbury and Epstein, 1986; Kumar and Sharma, 1990) and the toxic effects of specific ions (Cramer et al., 1994) likely contribute to the overall damage caused by salinity, as noted by Essa (2002). In severe cases, soluble salts can create such a significant osmotic challenge, coupled with specific ion toxicities and ionic imbalances, that it can ultimately lead to plant death (Munns, 2002). To assess plant responses to salinity, researchers commonly introduce a sodium chloride ($NaCl$) solution into the growth medium, mimicking field saline environments. In this investigation, we employed a range of $NaCl$ solutions to evaluate the tolerance levels of sesame seedlings under salt stress. Our findings revealed tolerance across all tested salinity levels in sesame seeds. Interestingly, a linear relationship emerged between salt tolerance and increasing salt concentrations. Statistical analysis confirmed significant differences in response to the salinity treatments among all the sesame varieties tested. The present study demonstrates that sesame's salt tolerance diminishes as salinity levels increase, although it still shows the ability to germinate under saline conditions. It is crucial to recognize that evaluating salt tolerance during the germination stage may offer limited insights into the overall crop salt tolerance. Many germination studies are conducted in controlled laboratory environments using petri dishes with different salinity solutions. Observations indicate that some crop plants

can shift from displaying salt-tolerant mechanisms during germination to becoming more salt-sensitive as they advance to the vegetative growth stage.

5. Conclusion

The osmotic stress induced by elevated salinity negatively impacts sesame germination and early seedling development. High salt concentrations hinder water uptake by the seeds, leading to delayed germination and diminished seedling vigor. This study observed a salinity tolerance gradient in sesame genotypes, where lower salinity levels promoted robust germination. However, germination percentage and seedling health metrics declined as salinity intensified. Notably, the response to increasing salinity varied across physiological parameters, with seedling biomass exhibiting resilience but relative injury rate escalating. Interestingly, the impact of slight salinity on shoot elongation (height) was very less, demonstrating a potential for enhanced salt tolerance in sesame under moderate salinity stress. However, the early seedling growth stage displayed only moderate salt tolerance. These findings underscore the crucial role of cultivating sesame cultivars with specific salinity tolerance adaptations. Selecting sesame varieties based on a region's pedological (soil) characteristics and implementing established cultivars known for their tolerance levels and agronomic traits are essential for optimizing yield potential. This research provides valuable insights into the interplay between salinity levels and diverse sesame cultivars' germination and seedling development. The observed variations in salt tolerance highlight the significance of maintaining genetic diversity within breeding programs to develop robust, salt-tolerant sesame varieties for future agricultural sustainability.

Acknowledgment

I would like to express my gratitude to Muhammad Amjid for helping obtain the study's observations.

References

- Abbasdokht, H., Ashrafi, E., Taheri, S., 2012. Effects of different salt levels on germination and seedling growth of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) cultivars. *International Journal of Agriculture and Crop Sciences*, 4(15): 1110–1114.
- Açıkbaş, S., Özyazıcı, M.A., Bıçakçı, E., Özyazıcı, G., 2023. Germination and seedling development performances of some soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) cultivars under salinity stress. *Turkish Journal of Range and Forage Science*, 4(2): 108–118.
- Ahmadvand, G., Soleimani, F., Saadatian, B., Pouya, M., 2012. Effects of seed priming on germination and emergence traits of two soybean cultivars under salinity stress (*Glycine max* L.). *International Research Journal of Applied and Basic Sciences*, 3(2): 234–241.
- Ahmed, R., Islam, M.M., Sarker, H.M.U., Hasan, M., Hossain, M.R., Shila, A., Ahammed, R., 2023. Morphological responses of three contrasting soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) genotypes under different levels of salinity stress in the coastal region of Bangladesh. *Journal of Plant Stress Physiology*, 9: 18–26.
- Ashraf, M., Shahbaz, M., Ali, Q., 2021. Drought and salinity-induced changes in antioxidant enzymes and their relevance to salt-tolerance in sesame. *Plant Physiology Reports*, 26: 1–10.
- Bahrami, H., Razmjoo, J., 2012a. Effect of salinity stress on germination and early seedling growth of ten sesame cultivars (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*, 2: 529–537.
- Bahrami, H., Razmjoo, J., Jafari, A.O., 2012b. Effect of drought stress on germination and seedling growth of sesame cultivars (*Sesamum indicum* L.). *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*, 2: 423–428.

- Bekele, A., Besufekad, Y., Adegna, S., Yinur, D., 2017. Screening of selected accessions of Ethiopian sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) for salt tolerance. *Biocatalysis and Agricultural Biotechnology*, 9: 82–94.
- Cerda, A., Bingham, F.T., Hoffman, G.J. 1997., Interactive effect of salinity and phosphorus in sesame. *Soil Science Society of America Journal*, 41: 915–918.
- Cramer, G.R., Alberico, G.J., Smith, F.A., 1994. Salt tolerance is not associated with sodium accumulation of two maize hybrids. *Australian Journal of Plant Physiology*, 21: 675–692.
- Cuartero, J., Fernandez, R., 1999. Tomato and salinity. *Scientia Horticulturae*, 78: 83–125.
- Cui, C., Wang, Y., Yu, C., Zhang, L., Li, G., Zhang, H., 2021. Advances in research on sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.): A comprehensive review of breeding, genetics, genomics, and molecular biology. *Industrial Crops and Products*, 170: 113807.
- Dossa, K., Wei, X., Zhang, Y., Fonceka, D., Yang, W., Diouf, D., Zhang, X., 2017. Analysis of genetic diversity and population structure of sesame accessions from Africa and Asia as major centers of its cultivation. *Genes*, 8(12): 362.
- El Harfi, M., Hanine, H., Rizki, H., Latrache, H., Nabloussi, A., 2016. Effect of drought and salt stresses on germination and early seedling growth of different color-seeds sesame (*Sesamum indicum*). *International Journal of Agriculture and Biology*, 18: 1088–1094.
- Essa, T.A., 2002. Effect of salinity stress on growth and nutrient composition of three soybean (*Glycine max* L. Merrill) cultivars. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science*, 188: 86–93.
- Farhoudi, R., Tafti, M.M., 2011. Effect of salt stress on seedlings growth and ions homeostasis of soybean (*Glycine max*) cultivars. *Advanced Environmental Biology*, 5: 2522–2526.
- Flowers, T.J., 2004. Improving crop salt tolerance. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 55(396): 307–319.
- Flowers, T.J., Flowers, S.A., 2005. Why does salinity pose such a difficult problem for plant breeders? *Agricultural Water Management*, 78(1), 15–24.
- Hassan, M., Asghari, A., Jamaati-e-Somarin, Sh., Saeidi, M., Zabihi-e-Mahmoodabad, R., Hokmalipour, S., 2009. Effects of water deficit on drought tolerance indices of sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) genotypes in Moghan region. *Research Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 3: 116–121.
- Huang, J., Rozelle, S., 1995. Environmental stress and grain yields in China. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*, 77(4): 853–864.
- Hussain, M., Kumar, A., 2022. Germination and seedling growth of sesame cultivars under salinity stresses. *Current Agriculture Research Journal*, 10: 366–374.
- Jamil, M., Khan, M.A., Rehman, S.U., 2022. Germination and seedling growth of sesame under salt stress: A comparative study of genotypic responses. *Environmental and Experimental Botany*, 193: 104648.
- Khatun, M., Rahman, M.A., Hossain, M.A., 2019. Physiological and biochemical responses of sesame genotypes under salt stress. *Plant Stress*, 13: 100234.
- Kingsbury, R.W., Epstein, E., 1986. Salt sensitivity in wheat. *Plant Physiology*, 80: 651–654.
- Kumar, A., Sharma, B.K., 1990. Specific ion effect on germination and seedling growth of wild canary grass (*Phalaris minor* (L.) Retz). *Journal of Advanced Plant Sciences*, 3: 321–325.

- Le, L.T.T., Kotula, L., Siddique, K.H.M., Colmer, T.D., 2021. Na⁺ and/or Cl⁻ toxicities determine salt sensitivity in soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.), mungbean (*Vigna radiata* (L.) R. Wilczek), cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* (L.) Walp.), and common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.). *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 22: 1909.
- Munns, R., 2002. Comparative physiology of salt and water stress. *Plant, Cell & Environment*, 25: 239–250.
- Munns, R., Tester, M., 2008. Mechanisms of salinity tolerance. *Annual Review of Plant Biology*, 59(1): 651–681.
- Nassery, H., Ogata, G., Maas, E., 1979. Sensitivity of sesame to various salts. *Agronomy Journal*, 71: 595–597.
- Ndifon, E.M., 2013. Assessment of salt and drought stresses using soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) seedling as indicator. *Advances in Agriculture, Sciences and Engineering Research*, 3: 1102–1111.
- Nobre, R.G., Gheyi, H.R., Cardoso, J.A.F., Dantas, B.F., Barbosa, F.S., 2010. Crescimento e floração do girassol sob estresse salino e adubação nitrogenada. *Revista Ciência Agronômica*, 41(3): 358–365.
- Pathak, N., Rai, A.K., Kumari, R., Bhat, K.V., 2021. Value addition in sesame: A perspective on bioactive components for enhancing utility and productivity. *Phytochemistry Reviews*, 20: 1117–1133.
- Ramirez, R., Gutiérrez, D., Villafane, R., Lizaso, J.I., 2005. Salt tolerance of sesame genotypes at germination, vegetative, and maturity stages. *Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis*, 36(17–18): 2405–2419.
- Santos, D.B., Lima, G.S., Gheyi, H.R., Silva, F.A.L., Soares, L.A.A., Oliveira, L.M.A., 2012. Produção e parâmetros fisiológicos do amendoim em função do estresse salino. *Revista Idesia*, 30(2): 69–74.
- Shanko, D., Jatani, G., Debela, A., 2017. Effects of salinity on chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) landraces during germination stage. *Biochemistry and Molecular Biology Journal*, 3(2): 9.
- Shitole, S.M., Dhumal, K.N., 2012. Effect of water stress by polyethylene glycol 6000 and sodium chloride on seed germination and seedling growth of *Cassia angustifolia*. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 3: 528–531.
- Tabatabaei, S.A., Naghibalghora, S.M., 2014. The effect of salinity stress on germination characteristics and changes of biochemically of sesame seeds. *Cercetări Agronomice în Moldova*, 48: 61–68.
- Tafouo, V.D., Wamba, O.F., Youmbi, E., Nono, G.V., Akoa, A., 2010. Growth, yield, water status, and ionic distribution response of three bambara groundnut landraces (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc.) grown under saline conditions. *International Journal of Botany*, 6: 53–58.
- Tsegay, B.A., Gebreslassie, B., 2014. The effect of salinity (NaCl) on germination and early seedling growth of *Lathyrus sativus* and *Pisum sativum* var. *abyssinicum*. *African Journal of Plant Science*, 8(5): 225–231.
- Voigt, E.L., Gomes, F.M.S., de Souza, G.M., dos Santos, M.G., 2009. Source-sink regulation of cotyledonary reserve mobilization during cashew (*Anacardium occidentale*) seedling establishment under NaCl salinity. *Journal of Plant Physiology*, 166(1): 80–89.
- Wan, Y., Zhou, Q., Zhao, M., Hou, T., 2023. Byproducts of sesame oil extraction: *Composition, function, and comprehensive utilization*. *Foods*, 12(12): 2383.
- Yadav, R., Kalia, S., Rangan, P., Pradheep, K., Rao, G.P., Kaur, V., Pandey, R., Rai, V., Vasimalla, C.C., Langyan, S., 2022. Current research trends and prospects for yield and quality improvement in sesame, an important oilseed crop. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 13: 863521.

- Yasmeen, A., Saleem, M. H., Ullah, A., Rizwan, M., 2023. Potential of seed priming in enhancing salt tolerance of oilseed crops: Focus on sesame. *Agronomy*, 13(3): 732.
- Zhang, H., Zhao, Y., Zhu, J.K., 2020. Thriving under stress: How plants balance growth and the stress response. *Developmental Cell*, 55(5): 529–543.
- Zhang, H., Zhu, J., Gong, Z., Zhu, J.K., 2022. Abiotic stress responses in plants. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, 23(2): 104–119.
- Zheng, Y., Wang, Y., Wang, X., Liu, Q., Zhang, X., 2021. Sesamin and sesamol: A review of their physiological functions and mechanisms of action. *Phytotherapy Research*, 35(1): 17–28.

To Cite

Üstün, R., 2025. Effects of Salinity Stress on Germination and Seedling Growth in Sesame Genotypes. *ISPEC Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 9(3): 762-774.
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15812032>.
